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opaque spikelets. The longer panicles with more spikelets resulted in severe competition for photosynthates, which led to a higher proportion of opaque spikelets.

The application of 130-67-67 kg NPK ha⁻¹ and N in three splits to Basmati 385 resulted in higher grain yield with a higher

percentage of grain filling and normal kernels due to a considerable reduction in sterility, abortiveness, and chalkiness.

The adaptability of *Azolla mexicana* in the Ege region of Turkey

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The Ege region on the west coast of Turkey has a distinct climate—temperature ranges from 15 to 35 °C from the beginning of April to the first week of September, rainfall averages 500-600 mm, and relative humidity is 57%. Summer is warm and dry while winter is mild and rainy.

Of four different *Azolla* strains obtained (*A. microphylla* 4030, IRRI; *A. microphylla* 4089, China; *A. filiculoides* 1001; and *A. mexicana* 2026), *A. mexicana* 2026 was found adaptable to Izmir ecological conditions. In 1995, a field experiment was conducted to determine the suitable inoculation time for *A. mexicana*. *A. mexicana* was first grown at Izmir and then transferred to the rice experimental fields at Menemen (sandy loam soil, 0.9% organic matter, and pH 6.9). Rice variety TOAG-92 was used in the experiment.

Four different inoculation times were tested one after the other on the same plots. A randomized complete block design with three replications was used in the rice fields. For each application time, 300 g of fresh *Azolla* was inoculated per square meter and allowed to grow for 14 d. When the surface was covered with *Azolla* (7-10 d after inoculation), 0.2 g P₂O₅ m⁻² was applied. *Azolla* biomass was collected and fresh weight, dry weight, and total N were measured (Table 1). The first inoculation of *Azolla* was done when the rice plants were at the 3-leaf stage.

The inoculated amount of fresh weight (300 g m⁻²) increased to 1122 g m⁻² after 14 d (274%). Statistical analysis showed that the first inoculation dates resulted in comparatively better yield perfor-

mance than any other inoculation dates based on Duncan's multiple range test. The best time for *Azolla* inoculation was the first week of July (1200 g m⁻²) (see table). However, inoculating *Azolla* at the end of August also gave a reasonable amount of *Azolla*. N was 0.33% in fresh *Azolla*, and mean N gain was 2.7 g m⁻².

The effect of *A. mexicana* on soil N mineralization was also investigated in 1996. Incubation studies using fresh and dried *Azolla* were conducted in the laboratory. *Azolla* was placed on top of half of a sample of air-dried sandy loam soil in a test tube (2-cm-diam); the other half of the

soil was placed on top of the *Azolla* in another test tube. Both were flooded to a 5-cm depth with distilled water to keep the *Azolla* from floating. More *Azolla* was added to give about 5 mg N test tube⁻¹. Tubes were then incubated in the dark at 30°C. Results are shown in Table 2. N release was more rapid from dried *Azolla* (56%) than from fresh *Azolla* (38%). The *Azolla* totally decomposed after 2-3 wk and increased the total soil N by 38-56%, contributing to total soil organic matter. Organic matter release was more rapid from dried *Azolla* (40%) than from fresh *Azolla* (31%).

Table 1. Average growth and nitrogen accumulation in the *Azolla*-inoculated field plots, Izmir, Turkey, 1995.

Treatment	Inoculation date	Mean temperature (°C)	Amount harvested (g m ⁻²)	% increase in fresh weight	N increase (g m ⁻²)
1	10 Jul	30.0	1200 a	300	3.0 a
2	24 Jul	30.6	1090 bc	263	2.6 bc
3	7 Aug	27.4	1060 c	253	2.5 c
4	21 Aug	27.4	1140 ab	280	2.8 ab
Av		28.9	1122	274	2.7
SD				60	0.10

Table 2. Increase in total N and organic matter content of soil incubated with *A. mexicana*.

Week	Control soil	% increase			
		Total N		Organic matter	
		Fresh	Dried	Fresh	Dried
1	100	127.5 b	122.9 e	114.0 c	105.5 e
2	100	137.5 a	135.4 c	130.5 a	138.8 a
3	100	133.3 a	155.5 a	128.8 a	140.0 a
4	100	133.3 a	144.4 b	122.1 b	134.2 a
5	100	126.6 b	133.3 cd	114.2 c	125.5 c
6	100	122.2 c	131.1 d	108.6 d	120.3 d